

Enabling Portable Demand Flexibility Control Applications in Virtual and Real Buildings

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ABSTRACT

Control applications that facilitate Demand Flexibility (DF) are difficult to deploy at scale in existing buildings. The heterogeneity of systems and non-standard naming conventions for metadata describing data points in building automation systems often lead to ad-hoc and building-specific applications. In recent years, several researchers investigated semantic models to describe the meaning of building data. They suggest that these models can enhance the deployment of building applications, enabling data exchanges among heterogeneous sources and their portability across different buildings. However, the studies in question fail to explore these capabilities in the context of controls. This paper proposes a novel semantics-driven framework for developing and deploying portable DF control applications. The design of the framework leverages an iterative design science research methodology, evolving from evidence gathered through simulation and field demonstrations. The framework aims to decouple control applications from specific buildings and control platforms, enabling these control applications to be configured semi-automatically. This allows application developers and researchers to streamline the onboarding of new applications that could otherwise be time-consuming and resource-intensive. The framework has been validated for its capability to facilitate the deployment of control applications sharing the same codebase across diverse virtual and real buildings. The demonstration successfully tested two controls for load shifting and shedding in four virtual buildings using the Building Optimization Testing Framework (BOPTTEST) and in one real building using the control platform VOLTTRON. Insights into the current limitations, benefits, and challenges of generalizable controls and semantic models are derived from the deployment efforts and outcomes to guide future research in this field.

1. Introduction

The International Energy Agency (IEA) estimates the need for a tenfold increase in Demand Flexibility (DF) by 2030 relative to 2020 levels, 50% of which is expected to come from buildings [1]. DF is characterized by active load management across different timescales to support grid demands, particularly during high demand, low supply, or risk of renewable curtailment [2]. DF strategies include load shifting and shedding, which can be triggered by grid signals such as time-varying electricity prices [3]. Given the increase of variable renewable energy sources, the more frequent, intense, and longer-lasting extreme weather events, the current energy supply disruptions worldwide, and their impact on grid reliability, DF control applications have gained greater attention [4, 5]. This is reflected in international directives and roadmaps, such as in the new reform of the European electricity sector [6] and the US national roadmap for grid-interactive efficient buildings [7].

Despite the potential, DF remains an underemployed resource, mostly applied in large consumers, research pilot projects, or residential buildings through direct load control programs [8–10]. Common challenges for adopting DF applications in buildings have been identified in the literature, for instance, by the IEA EBC Annex 82 working group [11]. Among these challenges, there is a lack of interoperable and portable applications, particularly supervisory controls that can react to grid signals. Supervisory control applications, such as for DF, are rarely deployed at scale due to the heterogeneous nature of the building stock, which leads to variations in the type of systems, data sources,

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51 communication protocols, and data formats [12]. While integrating these resources with control platforms can be fa-
52 cilitated through software solutions, configuring control applications predominantly relies on manual processes, which
53 increases overall technology costs. There is a substantial effort to discover and map data points to control platforms
54 due to the non-standard naming conventions used in Building Automation Systems (BAS) for the metadata that de-
55 scribe their data points [13, 14]. This process is usually ad-hoc and building-specific, limiting the interoperability and
56 portability of new applications [15, 16].

57 In industry, several Energy Management and Information Systems (EMIS) have gained attention and increased
58 adoption. These platforms are software layers built on top of the BAS, and they use semantic models to support point
59 mapping and configuration of applications [17]. These platforms leverage semantics to add context and meaning to
60 BAS metadata, making data points more discoverable and interpretable [18]. Among EMIS software solutions, Fault
61 Detection and Diagnostics (FDD) tools have the greatest market penetration. These tools use one-way communication
62 (read-only) to ingest BAS data and identify system faults [19]. Although very effective for data analysis, these tools
63 typically lack active control capabilities [20, 21]. Whilst recent research has investigated how to unlock their control
64 capabilities, studies have focused on automatic fault correction and improved control sequences for energy efficiency
65 rather than DF applications [22–24].

66 Research studies have explored the use of semantic models in assisting DF [9, 25–32]. However, their focus
67 has been primarily on data integration between heterogeneous resources from the building and grid sides and not on
68 how these models can be used to facilitate the configuration of DF control applications, which may assist with their
69 portability. Additionally, these studies have predominantly relied on semantic models based on custom-built metadata
70 schemas that are neither maintained nor open-source. Moreover, many of these research efforts require storing dynamic
71 data, such as measurement values, within the semantic models to apply semantic rules. This approach is considered
72 inefficient when large time-series data streams are involved [33, 34].

73 Further research has emphasized the promise of semantic models to automate the configuration of applications,
74 facilitating their portability and plug-and-play behavior across various buildings [13, 35]. Built on well-established
75 metadata schemas, semantic models can automate the mapping between applications and data points from different
76 buildings instead of having to hard-code them [36, 37]. Examples of such efforts include Mortar [38] and Energon
77 [39], which support the portability of analytic applications, as well as the multi-building data management platform
78 for energy analysis proposed in [40]. Nevertheless, the demonstration of automated configuration and portability of
79 control applications that require real-time data reading and writing, such as DF, remains limited. EFOnt has been
80 introduced to foster the DF domain standardization and allow the streamlined configuration of DF control applications
81 [41]. However, it is still in its early phases, with insufficient field demonstrations, expressivity, or alignment with other
82 schemas to adequately represent required BAS points and their interactions with building systems and spaces.

83 This paper aims to support the development and deployment of portable DF control applications by proposing
84 a semantics-driven framework. The framework addresses existing research gaps, especially the lack of approaches
85 that harness semantic models built upon established metadata schemas to streamline the configuration of DF control
86 applications while not requiring dynamic data to be stored in the models. This aims to facilitate the portability and
87 plug-and-play behavior of DF control applications across various buildings, as has been demonstrated in studies related
88 to analytic applications. To this purpose, this paper intends to answer the following research questions:

- 89 1. How can DF control applications be generalizable for different building system configurations and control plat-
90 forms?
- 91 2. How can semantic models of buildings contribute to an automated configuration of generalizable DF control
92 applications?
- 93 3. What are the benefits and challenges for the portability of generalizable DF control applications?

94 The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 presents a background and states the contributions
95 of this paper. Section 3 describes the methodology devised for the proposed semantics-driven framework. Section 4
96 presents two supervisory DF control applications and the virtual and real buildings used to demonstrate their deploy-
97 ment through the framework. Section 5 shows the results of the demonstration. Section 6 discusses the main findings
98 and how they address the research questions. Finally, Section 7 outlines concluding remarks and future research di-
99 rections.

2. Background and contributions

Portability within the context of buildings refers to the ability of a software application to be applied across different buildings [38]. To enable portability, controls must be developed in a generalizable manner with minimal dependency on individual building details, such as point names or control platforms. This can be supported by the capabilities offered by supervisory controls and semantic models. In this section, we provide the foundational background for these topics that form the basis of this paper’s contributions.

2.1. Supervisory controls

Supervisory controls can coordinate the operation of multiple building systems based on high-level objectives, such as maximizing load shedding to reduce consumption during high grid demand [35]. This is generally accomplished by having the supervisory controls derive optimal, high-level setpoints that are then communicated to lower-level (local) controllers, which control equipment through traditional control loops. By allowing these high-level setpoints to adapt to varying building conditions, supervisory controls play a key part in enabling applications to be generalizable across different buildings. One key challenge in achieving this is to create a seamless connection between these local controls, measurement data points, and external data sources with the control platforms hosting supervisory controls [14].

Supervisory controls can be developed, tested, and deployed in virtual and real buildings using different platforms (i.e., simulation, BAS, or EMIS). For instance, the Building Optimization Testing Framework (BOPTTEST) exemplifies a simulation platform for testing advanced control applications [42]. BOPTTEST integrates realistically modeled buildings and exposes their control interface through an API that resembles that of a BAS. This allows control applications to interact with BOPTTEST simulations as if they were controlling a real building [35]. VOLTRON [43] is an example of an EMIS platform that collects heterogeneous data to perform analytics and execute control strategies, seamlessly integrating with BAS platforms. The mapping of required data points from multiple sources and the portability of supervisory control applications across buildings integrated with these platforms can be facilitated by semantic models.

2.2. Semantic models

Semantic models are data models built on metadata schemas that offer machine-readable, structured, and unambiguous data definitions. These schemas are typically represented as graphs and rely on technologies such as Resource Description Framework (RDF)¹, Web Ontology Language (OWL)², and Shapes Constraint Language (SHACL)³. In the building domain, metadata schemas such as Brick[44], REC[45], SAREF[46], and the upcoming ASHRAE 223P [18, 47] can represent buildings, their spatial aspects (e.g., thermal zones), equipment (e.g., chiller), including their components (e.g., fans), measurement and control points (e.g., sensors and setpoints), and the relationship between them.

When we represent the data points of buildings using semantic models, these models can then be employed to configure (instantiate) control applications for each building [35]. This is enabled by an approach known as Ontology-based Data Access (OBDA) that allows applications to use uniform SPARQL⁴ queries across different data sources to discover and map required data points, instead of relying on hard-code metadata customized to each case [48]. For instance, a control application can be specified for a generic zone with abstract point names to define its inputs (e.g., related temperature measurements) and outputs (e.g., related temperature setpoints). Then, SPARQL can use common data definitions from the models to assist in mapping the application to specific zones and their respective sensor and control points within a building.

While maintaining time series and real-time data points in their original sources (e.g., BAS platforms or databases), the OBDA approach allows to query the semantic models for their external references (e.g., foreign key, time series identifier, pub-sub topics), as embedded in the models [18]. Interpreting these references can be outsourced to interfaces that connect the applications to the platforms running them, which should determine how to read or write in their data points, such as by using API requests.

The effective use of semantic models to configure control applications relies on the ability of these models to capture their metadata requirements (e.g., needed points and their relationships). Defining metadata requirements based on SHACL constraints has shown the potential to avoid ambiguous interpretation and facilitate reproducible

¹<https://www.w3.org/RDF/>.

²<https://www.w3.org/OWL/>.

³<https://www.w3.org/TR/shacl/>.

⁴<https://www.w3.org/TR/rdf-sparql-query/>

Figure 1: Semantics-driven framework illustrating the main components and phases that guide the development and deployment of DF control applications that are portable across heterogeneous buildings.

147 model validation [37]. Based on SHACL, the work from [37] has provided a semantic validation algorithm, referred
 148 to as Building Metadata Ontology Interoperability Framework (BuildingMOTIF), which can verify whether a given
 149 model meets the metadata required by different applications.

150 2.3. Contributions of this paper

151 This paper proposes a semantics-driven framework for enabling portable DF control applications. The framework’s
 152 main objectives are to create requirements for making supervisory controls more generalizable and to explore ways
 153 of using semantic models to facilitate their semi-automatic configuration in various buildings. The framework also
 154 employs control platform-oriented interfaces, which link the generalizable control applications to building data points,
 155 allowing them to abstract building- and platform-specific aspects. In summary, the contributions of this paper include:

- 156 • a method for developing generalizable control applications, identifying their metadata requirements, and vali-
 157 dating their suitability in different buildings
- 158 • a configuration process that allows DF control applications to be self-configured and customized (when needed)
 159 to individual buildings
- 160 • a demonstration of the portability of DF control applications across heterogeneous buildings without extensive
 161 reprogramming
- 162 • an open-source implementation of all of the above⁵

163 3. Methodology

164 This section outlines the methodology devised for the proposed framework, which facilitates developing and de-
 165 veloping DF applications portable across heterogeneous buildings. The main phases of the framework include devel-
 166 opment, validation, and cross-platform deployment (Figure 1), all of which are described in detail in the following
 167 sections. The framework serves as a guide for application developers and researchers, offering insights into the de-
 168 velopment and deployment of portable applications. The design of the framework was based on an iterative design
 169 science research approach [49], being greatly influenced by studies on application-driven semantic models [37] and
 170 cross-platform frameworks used in mobile app deployment [50, 51]. The framework went through several iterations
 171 guided by evidence gathered from simulation and field demonstrations prior to the final design.

⁵<https://github.com/LBNL-ETA/DFLEXLIBS>

3.1. Development of control applications

In order for control applications to be portable across heterogeneous buildings, they need to be generalizable. In this section, we propose a method for developing generalizable control applications through a set of defined requirements, and for identifying their metadata needs through SHACL.

3.1.1. Develop generalizable controls

Generalizable controls are referred to in this paper as controls capable of being readily applicable in a wide range of buildings, system types, and control platforms without extensive customization. Being easy to deploy means that the software used to implement these controls should rely on reusable foundational scripts, minimizing the need for labor-intensive reconfiguration efforts. To develop control applications capable of delivering these desired outcomes in our framework, we established the following requirements.

- **Adaptable to changing operating conditions:** for a control to be generalizable to a large set of buildings, it must account for changing operating conditions that buildings might encounter [52]. This is crucial because making incorrect assumptions about current conditions (e.g., a predetermined occupancy schedule) can result in improper control actions' decisions. Supervisory controls can support this requirement by allowing systems to be managed based on diverse monitoring conditions such as occupancy schedules and status, comfort and faulty conditions, HVAC modes, grid signals, and specific constraints, including "hands-off" zones or specific DF settings.
- **Flexible to available data:** to further automate the portability process while minimizing user intervention, control applications need the ability to be configured based on available data [53]. This can be realized by employing methods that enhance the flexibility for querying new data while simultaneously enabling the controls to adapt accordingly.
- **Abstract to specific buildings:** to minimize reconfiguration efforts while making controls portable, these controls must be designed in a way that they are not tied to a specific building's context [35]. For that, applications must exclusively contain control logic, regardless of buildings and their specific control platforms' vendors, communication protocols, point naming practices, and data accessing methods. This can be supported by developing applications based on consistent, abstract, and easily queryable metadata rather than hard-coded point naming. To enhance portability and to support semantic validation processes that can help identify and handle data inconsistencies across buildings, this metadata should be based on well-established schemas and be formalized as requirements in an explicit and machine-readable way.
- **Built on modular functions:** to effectively reduce the efforts associated with developing multiple generalizable controls, these controls should be composed of self-contained, modular functions that can be shared across them. Software solutions that are highly modularized can improve adaptability, enhance extensibility, and increase the potential for reuse [54]. To facilitate this, these functions should abstract not only buildings and control platforms' particularities but also the control applications.

Fulfilling these requirements should allow controls to be more easily applied to a diverse set of buildings without requiring extensive customization. Nevertheless, it should be noted that some applications are better suited for specific systems and lack complete generality. For instance, adjusting chiller setpoints strategies in cooling plants only applies to built-up chillers, commonly found in larger commercial buildings. In addition, these requirements are based on the authors' informed judgments, which are drawn from our expertise, a comprehensive review of existing literature, and insights gained while demonstrating this work. While it is crucial to acknowledge their inherent subjectivity and potential uncertainty, they are valuable for driving future development and research in this field. In Figure 2 and in the following sections, we explore how we meet these requirements within the proposed framework.

Figure 2 illustrates how our framework allows supervisory controls to share modular functions and be portable across different buildings through interfaces and semantic models. To develop these supervisory DF controls, this paper builds upon the existing work [55] and the ongoing efforts by the authors in providing common sequences of operation for HVAC-based DF applications. The description for two of them implemented and tested in this study is presented in Section 4.

Figure 2: Simplified illustration of modular supervisory control applications sharing functions and interacting with buildings via interfaces and semantic models. The spectrum on the right demonstrates the transition from abstract functions to specific buildings and control platforms.

219 3.1.2. Identify metadata requirements

220 Data requirements for control applications are often defined in English-language documents, such as ASHRAE
 221 Guideline 36, which describes the minimum points needed to implement their control sequences [56]. However, to
 222 avoid ambiguity issues and enable semantic-based validation and configuration of applications, data requirements
 223 must be described based on their metadata (context) [37]. For example, to adjust deviations from comfort levels while
 224 deploying a load shed control, an application must identify not only its inputs (temperature and the range of permitted
 225 setpoints values) and outputs (temperature setpoints) but their context as well. This can include relationships with
 226 building spaces or systems, and external references to access the points in their respective sources.

227 Our work proposes formalizing metadata requirements using the SHACL standard based on the Brick schema. The
 228 selection of Brick is due to its ability to capture metadata required in various control strategies and analytics [15, 57],
 229 as well as its open-source nature, widespread use in the research community [58] and support by an industry con-
 230 sortium [18]. Nevertheless, the framework can be extended to other metadata schemas without significant changes.
 231 Algorithm 1 gives an example of a formalized definition of metadata requirement using SHACL. It requires a seman-
 232 tic model to have zones (`brick:Zone`) with at least one (`sh:qualifiedMinCount 1`) point (`brick:hasPoint`) of the type
 233 "temperature sensor" (`brick:Air_Temperature_Sensor`) and at least one (`sh:minCount 1`) external reference relationship
 234 (`ref:hasExternalReference`). Once defined for all control inputs and outputs, these SHACL metadata requirements can
 235 be used to validate that a given building, described by a semantic model, can support a specific control application.

236 3.2. Semantic sufficiency validation

237 To validate the suitability of a control for a given building based on its semantic model, our framework uses the
 238 BuildingMOTIF toolset⁶ [37]. In this section, we describe how this toolset is used for validation and how to update
 239 the models based on the generated report.

240 3.2.1. Validate semantic models

241 During the validation, the BuildingMOTIF toolset can help automate the comparison between the control's meta-
 242 data requirements expressed with SHACL constraints and the metadata available in semantic models of specific build-

⁶<https://nrel.github.io/BuildingMOTIF/README.html> ALPHA release

Algorithm 1: Snippet of a formalized definition of metadata requirement using SHACL constraints. The @prefix notations establish namespaces for referencing external data schemas when applying rules.

```

1 @prefix owl: <http://www.w3.org/2002/07/owl#>.
2 @prefix sh: <http://www.w3.org/ns/shacl#>.
3 @prefix brick: <https://brickschema.org/schema/Brick#>.
4 @prefix ref: <https://brickschema.org/schema/Brick/ref#>.
5 @prefix df: <urn:df_constraints/>.
6 df:zone a sh:NodeShape, owl:Class;
7   sh:targetClass brick:Zone;
8   sh:property [
9     sh:path brick:hasPoint ;
10    sh:qualifiedValueShape [
11      sh:class brick:Air_Temperature_Sensor ;
12      sh:qualifiedMinCount 1 ; ] ; .
13 df:timeseries-identifier a sh:NodeShape;
14   sh:targetClass brick:Air_Temperature_Sensor;
15   sh:property [
16     sh:path ref:hasExternalReference ;
17     sh:nodeKind sh:BlankNode ;
18     sh:minCount 1 ; ] ; .
    
```


Figure 3: Example of metadata requirements (SHACL) to validate the semantic model for a building using BuildingMOTIF.

243 ings. Figure 3 illustrates an example of metadata requirements (in SHACL) for a given control based on the Algorithm
 244 1. By comparing these requirements with a subset of available metadata from a semantic model, BuildingMOTIF
 245 scripts can provide feedback on missing metadata. In this case, it highlights the absence of an external reference
 246 connected to the zone temperature sensor, suggesting that the model needs to be updated to run the desired application.
 247 This clear and actionable feedback from the validation process helps to expedite error identification and troubleshoot-
 248 ing.

249 3.2.2. Update models if required

250 There are three potential reasons why a semantic model of a building might lack metadata. Firstly, it could be due to
 251 the absence of certain elements in the actual building, such as the absence of a return fan in an air handler. Secondly, the
 252 element may be present, but it lacks available or reliable metadata about it. For instance, a sensor might be collecting
 253 data, but the model lacks the metadata related to its access through the BAS API or communication protocol. Lastly,
 254 the element might exist and have data or metadata, but it has not been included in the semantic model for some reason.
 255 In this case, the modeler may have chosen not to incorporate certain types of sensors in the first version of the model.
 256 In situations where the second or third scenario applies, the semantic model needs to be updated with the missing
 257 metadata, to run the selected application. Ideally, experts responsible for the semantic model of the building should

Figure 4: Snippet of a semantic model of a given building and sample of a query to retrieve the external references from zone temperature sensors needed for the DF control application. Adapted from [60].

258 support and execute this update. This way, we can reduce the workload on application developers. The process can be
 259 done by explicitly adding those missing metadata in the model or using another capability from the BuildingMOTIF
 260 toolset, which can help automate the correction of a model. This correction autogenerates templates based on the
 261 missing metadata and adds them as new concepts in the semantic model. Successfully passing the semantic validation
 262 for all metadata requirements ensures that a semantic model is comprehensive enough to allow the configuration of
 263 required inputs and outputs of a control application.

264 3.3. Cross-platform deployment

265 Once validated, the deployment of control applications in distinct platforms (e.g., simulation, BAS, and EMIS)
 266 relies on their different methods of accessing and interacting with building data points [59]. For instance, while one
 267 platform may allow accessing its points through external time series databases, others can offer direct access to publish-
 268 subscribe topics or BACnet objects on a network. To ensure that control applications can effectively be configured to
 269 read and write data in heterogeneous buildings, it is important to have platform-oriented interfaces. These interfaces
 270 can decouple generalizable control applications from specific buildings while enabling any required customization in
 271 their configuration and deployment. In this section, we present how our framework allows the applications to be self-
 272 and custom-configured for reading and writing data in given buildings and the role of the interfaces in this.

273 3.3.1. Self-configure

274 To streamline the deployment of control applications within given buildings, our framework leverages their seman-
 275 tic models to self-configure them as much as possible. Enabling self-configuration involves using SPARQL queries
 276 to establish mappings between abstract point names defined in the applications and their corresponding physical or
 277 virtual counterparts in different buildings.

278 An example of a SPARQL query used for this purpose is illustrated in Figure 4. On the left side of the figure is
 279 a SPARQL query looking for external references to access zone temperature sensor points for an arbitrary number of
 280 zones in a particular control platform. This SPARQL query can be derived from the SHACL shapes, which already
 281 define the metadata needed for applications, and be supplemented by concepts that define how the current interfaced
 282 platform allows access to its points (i.e., in this example, via a `ref:hasTimeseriesId` relationship). On the right side of
 283 the figure is a snippet of a semantic model instantiating concepts and relationships from Brick to describe a temperature
 284 sensor point in a given zone. The answer for the query gives the zone point references to external sources as embedded
 285 in the queried model, including “temp_logger_101” for “hvac_zone_1”. Using similar queries to satisfy all metadata
 286 requirements of an application allows one to self-configure it for different buildings, reducing the reliance on manual
 287 setup.

3.3.2. Custom-configure

Although supervisory controls can help generalize applications, data availability and constraints may differ between buildings. For example, knowledge of the current HVAC operating mode (heating or cooling) is required to determine the appropriate setpoint adjustments. One building may expose this information as a data point, while another may require this to be inferred. Custom functions to determine control inputs may be needed in these cases. In addition, to accommodate their unique needs, certain buildings may require custom-designed control flows, which may require control outputs to be modified in a given way, such as prioritizing zones or equipment. Moreover, certain applications may require metadata not covered by the chosen metadata schema, not allowing them to be self-configured. Those could involve considerations concerning DF, such as minimum and maximum activation duration for load shedding [61], not often present in building-centric metadata schemas. Our work acknowledges the need for these customizations, allowing tailored functions to be integrated with generalizable control applications through the interfaces. For example, having applications that only rely on the operating mode values, being agnostic on how they are estimated. We also provide a set of templates for configuration files that can incorporate building-specific constraints not covered by the semantic models, while ensuring that they can be managed in a normalized way by the interfaces.

3.3.3. Read and write data

To complete the setup for deploying control applications in different buildings and on various control platforms, we must establish their connections. This is achieved through interfaces specifically designed for each control platform, tailored to their methods of accessing and interacting with building data points. Based on these methods, the interfaces can interpret the point's external references originating from the semantic queries and configuration files, enabling the required data by the applications to be read and written accordingly in different buildings.

3.3.4. Reuse controls

The configuration and deployment of the control applications through the interfaces are crucial in enabling their reuse in various buildings. Figure 5 summarizes the sequence of actions the interfaces perform through a 5-step workflow. Step 1, the interfaces import custom data and metadata from configuration files for each building (e.g., getting DF implementation constraints). Step 2, the interfaces query the semantic modes to self-configure the application with common metadata (e.g., related to building data points). Step 3, the interfaces get the available measurement data (in some cases, iterating over each zone). They use the external references obtained by the semantic queries or defined in the configuration files and interact with the data points according to the control platform (e.g., sending RESTful requests). Step 4, the interfaces call the control applications and custom functions scripts, passing the required processed data. Step 5, the interfaces post new control signal data in the control platforms. Then, the interfaces repeat steps 3 to 5 in a loop for the length of the control execution period.

By employing supervisory, generalizable control applications in step 4, the interfaces can decouple them from specific building data points and the communication methods of given control platforms. This allows for streamlining the portability of DF control applications across diverse buildings, helping to minimize reprogramming efforts in the process.

4. DF controls development and deployment across simulation and field testbeds

To demonstrate the portability of the proposed framework, we created two control applications and tested them in five virtual and real facilities. These buildings consist of one residential and four commercial buildings, spanning various locations, floor areas, HVAC systems, baseline controls, boundary and operating conditions, and control platforms (BOPTTEST and VOLTTRON). In this section, we describe both applications and the simulation and field testing performed.

4.1. Control applications development

The two proposed applications perform zone temperature adjustments. The first application focuses on load shedding, while the second addresses load shifting. Load shedding entails reducing building demand for a short period of time during shed events, which typically coincident with electric power system peaks, such as extremely hot summer afternoons [62]. Load shifting is the ability to change the timing of electric demand, often moving consumption from peak periods to off-peak times [62]. Shift is frequently implemented as a combination of a "take strategy" that increases energy consumption (e.g., pre-cooling in the morning) and a "shed strategy" (e.g., relaxing setpoints during the hot

Figure 5: 5-step workflow for configuring and deploying generalizable control applications in the interfaces.

Figure 6: Relaxing thermal comfort requirements by adjusting permitted setpoint range (minimum and maximum bounds) during a DF shed event. Adapted from [55].

336 summer afternoons) [63], which reduces energy use, compared to a baseline. Shed and take conditions can be commu-
 337 nicated as events with a clear start and end or via prices, which need to be interpreted by a logic and mapped to event
 338 conditions (e.g., price above \$1/kWh is considered a shed event). In this paper, we will use prices to communicate
 339 grid needs.

340 4.1.1. Shed control strategy

341 Shed control strategies can reduce demand by allowing the temperature to "float" to a more relaxed setpoint, which
 342 delays the operation of HVAC system [55], as shown in Figure 6. Its effectiveness depends on thermal comfort bound-
 343 aries, as well as internal and external heat gains [64].

344 Algorithm 2 presents a pseudo-code representation of the proposed control application. This application was
 345 designed in a modular fashion, where self-contained functions were pieced together according to the chosen strategy.
 346 The application begins with a function that relaxes the comfort range for DF event periods with customized offset
 347 values. Then, it includes a function that assesses the thermal comfort of different zones. If the zone temperature

348 is within the expanded temperature band, it is considered eligible for DF control. If the zones are eligible, another
 349 function evaluates the current grid signal and assesses if a load shed event has started (i.e., if the price is above a
 350 threshold estimated as the third quartile of the input price distribution). The shed function computes new setpoints
 351 according to the current HVAC operation mode and the zone setpoints. If no shed event is detected or the zones are
 352 not eligible for DF controls, the application releases the control, which means it incrementally returns the setpoints to
 353 their baseline values.

Algorithm 2: Pseudo-code for the zone temperature adjustment application performing load shedding.

```

1 relaxComfortRange;
2 if ComfortCheck then
3   if ShedEvent then
4     if HeatingMode then
5        $newSetpoint \leftarrow computeHeatSetpoint$ 
6     else
7        $newSetpoint \leftarrow computeCoolSetpoint$ 
8   else
9      $releaseDFControl$ 
10 else
11    $releaseDFControl$ 

```

354 4.1.2. Shift control strategy

355 Pre-cooling or pre-heating a building to shift energy is more effective in high-mass buildings, where thermal inertia
 356 allows to slow down the temperature (rise or dip) when the setpoints are relaxed [65]. The magnitude of the energy
 357 shifted is also a function of outside temperature, outside air flow rate, internal heat gain, and solar heat gains [63].

358 Algorithm 3 outlines a pseudo-code example of the proposed application that adjusts zone temperatures while
 359 performing load shifting (i.e., take and shed). Built upon Algorithm 2, this control logic includes a new take event
 360 function. This function evaluates the potential for load increase based on a combination of future price signals, occu-
 361 pancy patterns, and the current zone temperatures. The concept of "future" can be customized by setting a specific time
 362 horizon, indicating when the application can begin to check for appropriate conditions (e.g., 3 hours before high-price
 363 periods). If, at this future time, the price surpasses a certain threshold, and the zone is expected to be occupied, while
 364 the current temperature remains within the comfort range, the function will recognize the need to start pre-heating
 365 or pre-cooling the building. Then, the application computes a new setpoint based on the current season and zone
 366 temperature setpoints.

367 4.1.3. Metadata requirements

368 The metadata requirements for both control strategies include temperature sensors, temperature setpoints, minimum
 369 and maximum temperature setpoints, and occupancy sensors related to zones, as well as price signals, DF constraints,
 370 and external references to access all of them. For those metadata requirements that have corresponding concepts in the
 371 Brick schema, they were translated to SHACL, as described in Section 3.1.2, and are available in our online repository⁷.
 372 The use of these requirements for semantic validation against the tested buildings is further detailed in Section 4.3. For
 373 those metadata requirements that are not captured by the Brick schema, they were not accounted for in the semantic
 374 validation analysis but were included in the templates provided for the custom configuration files. Among them were
 375 the references needed to access grid signals from external data sources and constraints related to DF implementation.

376 4.2. Simulation and field testbed

377 In our simulation testing, we used four virtual buildings, realistically modeled and validated in BOPTTEST [42].
 378 Table 1 presents an overview of the locations, areas, zones, types, and HVAC systems of the tested buildings. More

⁷<https://github.com/LBNL-ETA/DFLEXLIBS>

Algorithm 3: Pseudo-code the zone temperature adjustment application performing load shifting and shedding.

```

1 relaxComfortRange;
2 if ComfortCheck then
3   if TakeEvent then
4     if HeatingSeason then
5        $newSetpoint \leftarrow computeHeat.Setpoint$ 
6     else
7        $newSetpoint \leftarrow computeCool.Setpoint$ 
8   else if ShedEvent then
9     if HeatingMode then
10       $newSetpoint \leftarrow computeHeat.Setpoint$ 
11    else
12       $newSetpoint \leftarrow computeCool.Setpoint$ 
13  else
14     $releaseDFControl$ 
15 else
16    $releaseDFControl$ 

```

379 detailed information about these test cases can be found on the official BOPTEST page⁸.

Table 1: Overview of the tested virtual buildings

Building (label)	Location	Area	Zones	Type	HVAC System
Bestest air (B1)	Denver, USA	48 m ²	Single	Small commercial	Idealized four-pipe fan with heating coil served by a gas boiler and cooling coil served by a chiller
Bestest hydronic heat pump (B2)	Brussels, Belgium	190 m ²	Single	Residential	Air-to-water heat pump
Singl-zone commercial hydronic (B3)	Copenhagen, Denmark	8,500 m ²	Single	Small commercial	Air handling unit with heat recovery and radiant heating
Multi-zone office simple air (B4)	Chicago, USA	1,660 m ²	Multiple	Large commercial	Single-duct VAV system with heating coil served by a heat pump and cooling coil served by a chiller

380 In our field testing, we used VOLTTRON middleware, adding semantic models to its software architecture to
381 facilitate the portable deployment of applications [60]. The testing was performed in a small office building in the
382 US. Table 2 summarizes the location, area, zone, type, and HVAC systems of the building. More detailed information
383 about the characteristics of this building and its baseline control can be found on [60].

Table 2: Overview of the tested real building

Building (label)	Location	Area	Zones	Type	HVAC System
Office building (B5)	New York, USA	351 m ²	Single	Small commercial	Dual-fuel heating system of heat pumps and gas-furnace

⁸<https://ibpsa.github.io/project1-bopetest/testcases/index.html>.

Figure 7: Simplified demonstration of the semantic validation for the metadata requirements of the shift and shed control application versus the metadata available within the semantic models of each tested building.

4.3. Semantic validation

To validate the tested buildings against the metadata requirements from our developed controls, we created an interface to connect their semantic models and the SHACL constraints into BuildingMOTIF. For the virtual buildings, we generated semantic models for B1, B2, and B3 based on the foundation established in a previous study by the authors for modeling B4 [12]. These models are expected to not only contribute to this study but also advance the ongoing efforts within the BOPTTEST community towards an enhanced semantic understanding of its test cases [66]. For the real building, we generated its semantic model using the model creation feature of BuildingMOTIF [37].

Following the example from Section 3.2, Figure 7 illustrates the validation results from the BuildingMOTIF script applied in each building according to the controls’ metadata requirements listed in Section 4.1.3.

To account for the variability of the setpoint definitions in the different buildings, the SHACL constraints were set to accept either a single temperature setpoint or both heating and cooling setpoints. It also accounted for model structure variations, accepting either a direct relationship between zone and point or through equipment. An occupancy sensor point was unavailable for all the buildings, so the interfaces were customized to obtain data from their occupancy schedules instead. Moreover, the semantic model from the real building did not include accessible BAS data points for minimum and maximum temperature setpoints, so fixed values were added for them in the interfaces. With these additional customizations, all tested buildings were suitable for the application. Section 6 provides a more in-depth discussion of these customizations.

4.4. Cross-platform deployment

To allow the proposed controls to interact with the buildings, we created control platform-oriented interfaces that could import the instantiated configuration files, query the semantic models, and call the required custom functions of each building. To self-configure the controls, SPARQL queries similar to the example in Section 3.3.1 were applied for all metadata requirements of the applications. To custom-configure the controls as described in Section 3.3.2, a

few customizations were required.

In BOPTTEST, we had to create custom functions to identify their HVAC operating modes since the buildings had different systems and lower-level logic. In VOLTTRON, we needed to add another logic layer to our generalizable DF application. This combined the setpoint adjustments during shift and shed events with a staging (rotation) logic of the heat pump units to avoid simultaneous demand peaks. The logic considered priority levels assigned to each unit based on factors such as the temperature difference from the setpoint and the duration of their inactive period. In addition, as required, we imposed specific constraints to limit the duration of the shed event to a maximum of two hours.

To read and write data in the buildings, we enabled the interfaces to interact with their control platforms, as outlined in Section 3.3.3. For the virtual buildings, we used the BOPTTEST web service⁹ to send RESTful requests to GET and POST measurement data and new control signals, functioning similarly to a BAS. For the real building, we used a VOLTTRON agent¹⁰ to receive measurement data and execute control signals from and into the building points.

We simulated both DF control strategies (shed and shift) in the virtual buildings during predefined two-week periods aligned with the peak heating and cooling days of the buildings as set in the BOPTTEST testing scenarios. In all these cases, dynamic electricity prices were used to communicate grid needs. We tested the DF shift control strategy in the real building over a four-day period in March 2023, and used the building’s real time-of-use price structure to identify the grid needs.

5. Results

This section presents the portability results for applying zone temperature adjustment in the tested buildings. We only show the second control strategy (shift) in detail, but the results from the first control strategy (shed) applied to the virtual buildings can be found in the Appendix.

We analyze the portability of the shift control application across the five tested buildings by assessing its ability to adjust zone temperature setpoints based on monitored conditions and in response to grid signals, thereby enabling load shifting and shedding. The findings are presented in Figures 8 by the setpoint changes and Figure 9 by the load variations across all buildings. In the figures, the shed periods coincide with high energy price signals (yellow shade), while take periods are pre-configured before the shed period (gray shade). For the virtual buildings, a 3-hour period was defined. For the real building, both shift and take periods were limited to 2 hours.

Figure 8 demonstrates the zone temperature setpoint adjustments, including an increase for preheating the building during take and a decrease for reducing the heating loads during shed. The setpoint changes vary in each building based on factors such as occupancy profiles, price schedules, and thermal dynamics. The latter can be seen in B1 and B3, where the flexible setpoints oscillate due to temperature deviations from comfort values, which activate the comfort check function in various instances. This behavior showcases a fast thermal dynamic in the buildings, rapidly dissipating the energy accumulated during the take period, likely due to its low thermal mass. In building B5, we can observe the staging operations of the heat pumps through the variation in their setpoints. Although there is an instance when a manual override is shown, it is shortly counteracted by the control.

Figure 9 compares the baseline and flexible loads in each tested building. It refers to 15-minute load profiles averaged throughout the testing periods. The plot shows that buildings B2 and B4 experience increased peak loads during the take period when using the proposed control strategy. This increase can be attributed to their higher setpoints calculated for pre-heating the zones prior to occupancy. This pre-heating aimed to ensure an adequate temperature that allows for an extended shed period. Buildings B1 and B3 do not exhibit the same behavior. This might come from the 15-minute resampling interval applied, which might not have captured their highest peak values, or by external factors, including their lower-level control logic, which deserves further investigation for a comprehensive understanding. Nonetheless, this issue did not arise in the real building as its heat pump units continuously rotated their operation, enabling effective peak reduction. The effect of the comfort check function with many oscillations in the flexible load can also be seen in Figure 9, especially in B1 and B3.

These preliminary findings highlight the portability of generalizable DF control applications across diverse buildings, whether virtual or real. The controls could adapt to varying conditions, occupancy patterns, and grid signals with minimal reprogramming efforts (mostly on creating the platform-oriented interfaces and custom functions). Although the evaluation performance of the application is beyond the scope of this paper, the control implemented in the real building did not cause any occupant complaints (except for the one control override instance during the four days) and

⁹<https://ibpsa.github.io/project1-boptest/docs-userguide/api.html>.

¹⁰<https://volttron.readthedocs.io/en/main/agent-framework/agents-overview.html>.

455 was able to reduce electricity costs at the site by 27%, successfully demonstrating the potential of this framework for
456 delivering real DF control applications.

457 **6. Discussion**

458 This paper presents a novel framework that enables developing and deploying DF portable controls across diverse
459 buildings with reduced reprogramming effort. This was made possible by the capabilities of the supervisory, modular
460 controls, semantic models, and interfaces. In the subsequent subsections, we examine the initial research inquiries
461 within the context of the established framework and the obtained results.

462 **6.1. Generalization of DF control applications**

463 Although our work demonstrates the deployment of a generalizable DF application across different building system
464 configurations and control platforms, our analysis indicates that the idea of a comprehensive, portable control appli-
465 cation remains limited. Some level of customization has to be considered during the configuration of the applications.
466 In this section, we outline three main customization categories and explore how they are currently being tackled in
467 existing research and how we approach them in our framework.

468 **6.1.1. Baseline control and reliance on lower-level logic**

469 Supervisory controls often rely on lower-level logic that may vary among buildings according to their system
470 configurations, available sensor types, writing capabilities, and approaches to defining operating modes and scheduling
471 [15]. For instance, one building can use compressor speed to identify the operating mode while another can use supply
472 air temperature with a different logic. Understanding the baseline supervisory controls and their underlying logic in
473 different buildings is critical to ensuring the intended outcome of new applications that replace and interact with them.

474 A software to facilitate the configuration of analytic applications using computational quantities based on SHACL
475 rules and Brick concepts was designed in [53]. These quantities express various methods for obtaining data within a
476 building, including direct sensor observations, indirect computations based on many observations, and default values.
477 This could potentially help with the challenge of obtaining required data from various underlying logic. However,
478 due to the lack of standardization in these logic, with each new building, developers might need to incorporate new
479 computational quantities to express them. To tackle inconsistent control logic across different buildings, the Open-
480 BuildingControl (OBC) initiative aims to establish a foundation for uniform control implementation, developing and
481 encouraging tools, procedures, and standards (specifically ASHRAE 231P) [67]. This effort could serve as the basis
482 for defining reusable computational quantities within the software provided by [53]. The problem is that the OBC
483 initiative is currently in its developmental stages, so combining these works is not yet possible. Moreover, the software
484 by [53] does not clearly identify how the data from different control platforms, or that are not within Brick nor default
485 across buildings (e.g., shed offset value) can be handled for the same application.

486 In an effort to acknowledge these customization needs while easing the burden on application development, we use
487 control platform-oriented interfaces in our framework. These allow generalizable control applications to be detached
488 not only from site-specific control logic and constraints but also from diverse data accessing methods and the lack
489 of expressivity by the Brick schema. Particularly looking at site-specific control logic, the interfaces allow custom
490 functions to be easily handled and integrated with the generalizable control. For example, one Python-based module
491 has been created to store various logic for determining HVAC operation modes. Developers may readily access this
492 module to add new logic as needed. To select the applicable logic for a building, we can simply change 2 lines of code
493 in the interface. As long as the low-level logic in the buildings can be identified, this approach helps to easily represent
494 them and navigate the different options. This could be further enhanced using the portable computational quantities
495 by [53], which have not been tested for control applications. The other benefits of our interfaces are further described
496 in the next sections.

497 **6.1.2. Platform-specific dependencies**

498 Different control platforms often have distinct methods for accessing and modifying data (e.g., through APIs,
499 publish-subscribe messaging, or given communication protocol methods). Consequently, to enable applications to
500 be portable in buildings with distinct platforms, it is necessary to consider their intricacies and compatibility consid-
501 eration. Moreover, different platforms may use different programming languages or methodologies, such as visual
502 programming. Portable approaches must be based on a common programming language and methodologies to ensure
503 consistent control across various buildings.

504 The Mortar platform [38] was developed to create and assess analytic applications that can be portable across dif-
 505 ferent buildings. However, the current portability of this solution is limited to the buildings' data sets stored within the
 506 time series and Brick model databases linked to the platform. The investigation for additional databases or establishing
 507 connectivity with real-time data sources across different platforms, which is essential for control applications, has not
 508 been undertaken yet.

509 To leverage different data access methods, we implement interfaces that can be tailored to individual control plat-
 510 forms (such as VOLTTRON and BOPTEST). These interfaces, once created, may be easily reused across buildings
 511 sharing the same platform and across applications that require the same data points. That was realized in our demon-
 512 stration when we reused the BOPTEST interface across the four virtual buildings for the two controls by only chang-
 513 ing 3 lines of code. To facilitate deployment across various platforms while abstracting their different programming
 514 methodologies, our applications were developed in Python. Then, through each platform's data accessing methods,
 515 data exchange with the same control can be enabled as needed in different buildings.

516 **6.1.3. Site-specific constraints**

517 Deploying control applications, especially within real buildings, presents various challenges that can lead to errors
 518 and incorrect control actions. These can be related to inconsistent units of measurement, real-time data access delays,
 519 and missing data due to sensor unavailability, malfunctions, or communication issues. Despite these challenges being
 520 common across various buildings, their manifestations can vary and be site-specific. Hence, developing generalizable
 521 control functions to respond to them can be difficult. Moreover, in some cases, additional functions on top of DF
 522 applications are required in different buildings. For example, in the tested real building, an additional function had to
 523 be added to ensure the setpoint changes for DF were applied along with a staging operation of the heat pump units.

524 Existing controls often hard-code such site-specific constraints in the main control logic, resulting in applications
 525 that are not portable without extensive effort. Our framework includes a validation process that can help handle and
 526 normalize building inconsistency. This process can ensure that issues, such as those related to measurement units'
 527 mismatch and missing data due to sensor unavailability, are promptly reported during the control selection, allowing
 528 necessary (and possible) adjustments to be made before its deployment. Our framework may not offer straightforward
 529 solutions for challenges such as real-time data access delays or sensor failures due to emerging issues. Nonetheless,
 530 by allowing flexible semantic queries, it could be possible to support an adaptive control based on current conditions
 531 and alternative available data. In addition, our framework allows additional functions to be added on top of common
 532 DF applications in different buildings. They can be imported by the interfaces to use the outputs from the main DF
 533 control, handling the control signals as needed prior to sending them to the buildings.

534 **6.2. Automated configuration with semantic models**

535 While our work exploits semantic models and queries to self-configure the applications, we found that well-
 536 established building-centric metadata schemas [44–46] often lack essential metadata for running DF control appli-
 537 cations. Those include metadata related to weather forecasts, grid signals, and DF settings. Examples of the latter
 538 include maximum duration or temperature offsets for relaxing comfort range during shed events, as well as lead time
 539 to initiate shift (take) periods. As a result, fully automated control applications are not possible yet.

540 Existing solutions employ custom-built metadata schemas to accommodate DF-related information such as grid
 541 signals [9, 26, 28, 29]. However, these custom schemas are often unmaintained or not open-source, restricting their
 542 adaptability and reusability, especially when requiring extensions. The standardized SAREF metadata schema has
 543 *price* as one concept, but it falls short in establishing links to external time series data sources where this information
 544 is often available or in defining metadata for other grid signals and DF settings.

545 In our approach, we propose the use of template-based configuration files to systematically include missing meta-
 546 data needed for DF applications through the interfaces. Although not exhaustive, these templates are meant to contain
 547 only information that is not currently represented by well-established metadata schemas. This approach could also be
 548 well-suited to facilitate the setup of standard building-to-grid communication mechanisms such as openADR¹¹ and
 549 CTA-2045¹².

6.3. Benefits and challenges for portability of DF control applications

In order to better describe the benefits of our proposed framework, Figure 10 compares a traditional workflow for developing and deploying supervisory control applications with ours. A traditional workflow mainly consists of i) evaluating existing building systems (including their baseline controls) and user requirements, ii) discovering the buildings' data points (identifying their metadata, communication network and which are possible to be overridden), iii) developing a building-specific control logic based on (i) and (ii), iv) mapping the inputs and outputs from the control to these points (usually embedding them in the logic) and connecting with their related communication network, v) running and fine-tuning the control. In this workflow, each process is often bespoke, resulting in applications hard-coded to particular buildings. This makes it challenging to enable the portability of the same application in different buildings, often requiring one to redo most of the effort. Even when working within the same building, point mapping by one developer or for one application may be inadequate for another; they likely have to repeat them.

Our workflow proposes pre-processes, which may demand a labor-intensive effort but are highly reusable (one-time costs), and main processes, which are the ones repeated in different buildings but should be semi-automated with minimal user intervention and customization. The pre-processes include developing generalizable controls and building specific semantic models. The controls should be developed along with templates for their metadata requirements (in SHACL), SPARQL queries, and configuration files, and they need to adhere to our pre-established requirements, which involve being adaptable, abstract, flexible, and modular in nature. The building-specific semantic models should be based on a well-established, open metadata schema.

Our main processes include selecting and validating the suitability of generalizable controls for given buildings based on their required and available metadata. This step is semi-automated because for validating the suitability, it is also important to identify the data points that can actually be overridden in a building, any alternative to missing points the building may offer, and the user requirements. Once the control is selected, interfaces should be set to handle the required data according to the site-specific platform (communication network). To self-configure the application with the building point's external references, the SPARQL query templates for the chosen control can be adapted as needed. Then, using the template configuration files, the control can be customized by adding specific setting parameter values (e.g., DF constraints) and metadata not covered by the metadata schema. This process also involves connecting the application to site-specific custom functions through the interface. Successfully adhering to this streamlined workflow can simplify control configuration processes, minimize user involvement, and potentially reduce the deployment costs associated with portable control applications.

Despite the potential benefits of portable control applications, deploying them in real buildings presents several challenges. The generalizability of complex control applications, such as those involving distribution and plant-level controls, requires further investigation, especially to understand their required degree of customization. Furthermore, the current absence of semantic models in real buildings, and the inconsistent design choices to represent the same concepts, present additional barriers to achieving control application portability [68]. Other challenges lie in the limited writing capability of supervisory control when applied to overlay software platforms like EMIS into BAS, and in the lack of trust by building owners and operators in third-party applications overriding existing controls [24].

7. Conclusions and future work

There is a critical need for solutions that enable the scalable development and deployment of DF control applications, particularly in the context of achieving global decarbonization goals for buildings. This paper proposes a novel framework that defines the main requirements and processes to allow applications to be decoupled from specific buildings while enabling them to be self-configured with minimal reprogramming efforts. By integrating features from modular supervisory controls, semantic models, and platform-oriented interfaces, the framework can support application developers and researchers in streamlining the onboarding of new applications that could otherwise be time-consuming and resource-intensive.

We demonstrated the portability potential of the framework by deploying applications sharing the same codebase in various virtual and real buildings using BOPTEST and VOLTTRON. The framework successfully reduced reconfiguration efforts, requiring only minimal script modifications in most cases. Such modifications were required to accommodate the current limitations in achieving a comprehensive, portable control application. These limitations were discussed in detail, highlighting how our framework addresses them and providing valuable insights for future

¹¹<https://www.openadr.org/>.

¹²https://standards.cta.tech/apps/group_public/project/details.php?project_id=192.

research. In addition, although the applications proposed in this paper relate to DF controls, the framework may be widely adapted to other uses, including automated fault correction and advanced analytics.

Future work involves undertaking a more comprehensive validation of the framework in other real-world scenarios and performing an in-depth performance analysis of the controls to ensure their reliability and robustness. To further evaluate our framework, we aim to use software metrics grounded in computational complexity to quantitatively assess its benefits when compared with traditional workflows. Our future efforts also include creating an open-source library of reference DF control applications associated with various building archetypes. By linking the library of controls with our proposed framework, we will provide a comprehensive approach to the design and reuse of portable DF applications.

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Declaration of generative AI in scientific writing

During the preparation of this work, the authors used AI-powered tools, such as Grammarly and Quillbot, in order to improve readability and language in specific portions of the manuscript. After using this tool/service, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the publication.

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796 Appendix A Supplementary data

797 Figure A.1 demonstrates the zone temperature setpoint adjustments for performing only shedding across the four
798 virtual buildings simulated in BOPTEST, while Figure A.2 illustrates the corresponding load variations. The resulting
799 behavior closely resembles that of the shift and shed application, with the exception that there is no pre-heating or
800 cooling prior to load shedding.

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Figure 8: Adjustment in the zone temperature setpoints and activation of the flexible (shift and shed) control in an average day for the five tested buildings, as per Table 1 and 2. The gray and yellow shaded areas represent the shift and shed periods, respectively.

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Figure 9: Daily average power loads for the baseline and the flexible (shift and shed) control in the five buildings, as per Table 1 and 2. The gray and yellow shaded areas represent the shift and shed periods, respectively.

Figure 10: Comparison between a traditional and our proposed workflow for developing and deploying supervisory control applications.

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Figure A.1: Adjustment in the zone temperature setpoints and activation of the flexible (shed-only) control in a sample day for four tested buildings. The yellow shaded area represents the shed period, respectively.

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[figure]caption=bottom

Figure A.2: Daily average power loads for the baseline and the flexible (shed-only) control in the four virtual buildings. The yellow shaded area represents the shed period, respectively.